

Protocol for an umbrella review of systematic reviews on the relationship between gender discrimination and stereotypes

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Introduction

Gender discrimination is a deeply rooted problem that keeps affecting people's lives in many areas, from education to employment, from health care to legal systems. Although explicit forms of discrimination have been formally addressed in many legal frameworks, more subtle and hidden dynamics persist. These often manifest themselves through socially rooted stereotypes and prejudices, which contribute to the normalisation and legitimisation of unequal treatment based on perceived gender norms and roles. Stereotypes, defined as widely held assumptions about the traits, behaviours and social functions typically attributed to women and men, can act as cognitive heuristics shaping perception, reasoning and action. When such beliefs are influenced by emotional biases or negative evaluations, they give rise to prejudices, which in turn can lead to discriminatory practices. The interplay between mental representations and emotional dispositions is a key factor in understanding how gender biases are maintained and reproduced, both interpersonally and systemically.

In recent decades, research in psychology and related disciplines has increasingly focused on the mechanisms through which stereotypes and prejudices contribute to unequal outcomes. These research efforts extend to various fields, including recruitment processes, academic performance evaluations, healthcare provision and judicial decision-making. However, significant theoretical and methodological questions are still open: namely, how can we best measure their impact? To what extent do context and culture determine their expression? Furthermore, the distinction between implicit and explicit prejudices and the effectiveness of different intervention strategies continues to be central issues. Therefore, obtaining a more complex understanding of how stereotypes and prejudices act as precursors of gender discrimination is not only a theoretical challenge, but also a practical necessity. Such insights are essential to develop informed models of social cognition and to develop targeted, evidence-based measures to counteract prejudice, foster inclusion and promote gender equality in contemporary societies.

Methods

This umbrella review protocol has been developed in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA 2020). In accordance with the guidelines, the review of reviews protocol will be registered with the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO); moreover, in accordance with the FAIR Data Principles and Open Data policy endorsed by European Commission, this protocol will be published on EU Open Research Repository project community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/unveilgbd>). Ethical approval is not required for this work, as systematic reviews and meta-analysis only will be analysed.

The selection, screening and data extraction will be conducted through double-blind procedure

Search strategy

The research will be conducted on PubMed/MEDLINE, Scopus and Web of Science databases, using the search terms: (gender stereotyp* OR gender prejudice) AND (discrimination) AND (systematic review OR meta analysis OR meta-analysis). The search strategy might be slightly changed according to the different use of boolean operators within the different databases. Researcher will identify all systematic reviews and meta-analysis on the relationship between gender stereotypes or prejudices and discrimination. Literature search will be uploaded on Rayyan to be screened for inclusion and exclusion through a double-blind procedure.

A PRISMA flow-chart will be used to summarise study selection. Two different reviewers (GL, researcher, and CAB, student) will use the inclusion criteria to screen the titles and abstract, to identify all the potentially relevant studies. Full text will be retrieved where the exclusion criteria cannot be determined from the title/abstract screening for final selection. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion and consensus; if needed, any disagreement will be resolved by consulting a third reviewer (BB, researcher).

Exclusion Criteria

Systematic reviews and meta-analysis will be excluded if gender is not the focus of discrimination (e.g., race, sexual orientation) and if the study does not include gender stereotypes or prejudices directly related to discrimination. Only papers in Italian and English will be included. Papers whose title and abstract mention other forms of discrimination and gender (e.g., sexual orientation and trans people, black people and women) will be included only if gender is directly related to discrimination in the purposes of the study.

Data Extraction

The researchers will extract data from all the included papers, using a developed data extraction form. Disagreements will be resolved through discussions. Researchers will not be blind to the journal name or authors of the included reviews and meta-analysis. The extracted data will include: Bibliographical information (author(s), year, title, journal); Type of publication (meta-analysis, systematic review); Review aim; Criteria (Inclusion, Exclusion); Number of primary studies included; Methods (primary studies, synthesis methods); Variables; Results; Risk of bias assessment; Limits.